

Key Predictors of Near-Term T-Bill Yield Changes in Nigeria's Money Market

Abstract

This paper examines the drivers of short-term Treasury bill (T-bill) yield changes in Nigeria from 2006 to 2025, focusing on three key spreads that capture the interaction between monetary policy and liquidity conditions: the policy overhang (Monetary Policy Rate minus T-bill yield), interbank liquidity stress (Call rate minus MPR), and the funding curve slope (12-month minus 1-month deposit rates). Using monthly data and a combination of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) with Newey–West corrections and Jordà-style local projections, the study finds a stable and economically meaningful link between policy signals and market yields. About 8–15 percent of the gap between the policy rate and T-bill yields closes each month, confirming a gradual error-correction process in which market rates adjust toward the policy rate. Directional accuracy tests further reveal asymmetric behavior: when the policy overhang is positive, T-bill yields rise 41 percent of the time, but when negative, they fall 64 percent of the time, showing faster corrections when yields exceed the policy rate. Interbank liquidity stress has short-lived yet amplifying effects during tight market conditions, while the deposit slope provides a persistent signal of funding pressures, steeper curves forecast lower yields ahead, and inverted curves predict tightening. Local projection estimates confirm these patterns, with policy overhang effects sustained over several months, liquidity effects fading quickly, and funding-slope effects persisting for up to six months. Robustness checks across subsamples, alternative HAC specifications, and outlier adjustments affirm the stability of these relationships, emphasizing the complementary roles of policy stance, liquidity, and funding structure in shaping short-term interest rate movements in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Monetary Policy Transmission, Treasury Bill Yields, Interest Rate Spreads, Interbank Market Stress, Deposit Term Structure, Error-Correction Mechanism*

1.0 Introduction

In Nigeria, Treasury bill (T-bill) yields have long reflected how monetary policy decisions translate into real market outcomes. They influence how much the government pays to borrow, how investors value short-term assets, and how banks manage liquidity. Over the years, their movement has captured shifts in policy direction, liquidity pressures, and investor sentiment, revealing how closely money markets follow the Central Bank of Nigeria’s signals. The introduction of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) in 2006 marked a significant shift in how policy is communicated. Since then, the MPR has ranged from single digits to above 27% in recent years, and while T-bill yields generally move with it, they often lag or diverge in notable ways. Sometimes, the policy rate stands higher than T-bill yields, suggesting a tight policy that the market has yet to fully price in. At other times, short-term liquidity shortages push the interbank call rate above the policy rate, showing funding stress and prompting yield increases. These patterns illustrate how monetary conditions, liquidity, and expectations interact to influence short-term interest rates in Nigeria. Understanding what drives these fluctuations matters for both policymakers and investors. For the Central Bank, it reveals whether policy signals are effectively guiding market rates. For investors, it provides insights into future yield movements and an informed portfolio strategy.

However, despite their importance, the short-term drivers of Nigerian T-bill yields are not well-documented. Many studies focus on either policy rates or liquidity indicators alone, leaving little evidence on how the two combine to influence yield behavior. This paper aims to close that gap. Using monthly data from 2006 to 2025, it examines the drivers behind changes in T-bill yields, focusing on three spread indicators that capture policy stance and liquidity conditions: (i) a *policy rate–market rate spread* (hereafter referred to as policy rate overhang), capturing the gap between the MPR and T-bill yield; (ii) interbank liquidity stress, measured by the call rate–MPR spread; and (iii) a funding curve slope/deposit slope, defined as the difference between 12-month and 1-month deposit rates, which reflects liquidity preferences across maturities.

Figure 1 shows the movement of key money market rates over time. The black line represents the policy rate (MPR), the orange line shows the 91-day T-bill yield, and the magenta dashed line tracks the interbank call rate. Periods when the MPR sits above T-bill yields indicate policy overhang, while spikes in the call rate above the MPR suggest liquidity stress.

Figure 1: Key Money Market Rates in Nigeria (2006–2025)

These patterns often correct over time, hinting at predictable relationships that this paper investigates further. In light of these trends, the study explores three questions: Which spreads best predict short-term changes in T-bill yields? How does their influence vary under different liquidity conditions? And what can these results tell policymakers and investors about managing interest rate movements more effectively? To answer these questions, the paper employs several complementary approaches. It begins with correlation analysis to identify preliminary relationships among variables and then applies regression models, including baseline OLS with HAC corrections and Jordà-style local projections, to evaluate the strength, direction, and persistence of these relationships under different market conditions.

2.0 Brief Literature Background

Monetary policy transmission in Nigeria has been extensively studied, with a particular focus on how changes in the policy rate impact various market interest rates. Research has found that short-term interest rates respond most strongly to the MPR, albeit with some lag and occasional divergence (Awopegba et al., 2022). For example, using a vector autoregression, Kelilume (2014) reports an incomplete pass-through from MPR to market rates, but identifies a close relationship with interbank and T-bill rates. Similarly, Aliyu et al. (2018) find that the MPR has the most significant influence on the 91-day T-bill yield and the interbank call rate, compared to other rates in the economy. These studies confirm that Nigeria's short-term rates (including T-bills and interbank rates) are tightly, though not perfectly, anchored to the policy rate. However, they also note frictions – such as rigidities in retail deposit and lending rates – that can delay or dampen the transmission. This incomplete transmission often manifests as persistent spreads between the policy rate and market rates.

The notion that a policy rate–market rate spread can predict future rate adjustments aligns with the concept of an error-correction mechanism in interest rate dynamics (Engle & Granger, 1987; Hendry, Pagan & Sargan, 1984). In efficient money markets, deviations of market yields from the policy stance typically trigger corrective movements as rates converge toward equilibrium (Cottarelli & Kourelis, 1994; Mojon, 2000; Bernanke & Mihov, 1998). Empirical evidence from advanced economies reinforces this view. In addition, numerous studies have shown that yield curve spreads convey valuable information about future movements in short-term interest rates, consistent with the Expectations Hypothesis of the term structure. A steeper yield curve typically signals forthcoming rate increases, while an inverted yield curve often anticipates monetary easing (Mishkin, 1990; Hardouvelis, 1994). In emerging markets such as Nigeria, structural features including liquidity regulations, limited financial depth, and market segmentation often complicate the relationship between policy and market rates.

Nevertheless, local evidence suggests some predictive power in rate differentials. Sanusi (2010), using an error-correction model for Nigeria, found that the interbank rate adjusts rapidly to changes in the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), suggesting that large MPR–interbank spreads tend to be short-lived. This pattern aligns with the Central Bank of Nigeria's operating framework, in which the CBN uses open market operations and standing facilities to maintain interbank rates within a corridor around the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR). When interbank rates move above the upper corridor (MPR plus the symmetric band), the CBN typically injects liquidity to bring rates back down. On the other hand, when interbank rates fall below the lower corridor, the Bank absorbs excess liquidity through open market operations. The spread between the interbank call rate and the MPR, therefore, serves as a real-time indicator of liquidity conditions in the banking system, signaling periods of either funding pressure or excess liquidity. Another relevant body of research examines the information content of the term structure of interest rates in Nigeria. Most of these studies focus on the yield curve's ability to forecast macroeconomic outcomes such as output growth and inflation, rather than movements in interest rates themselves. (Samuel Oluwapelumi et al., 2021), for instance, finds that the spread between long-term bond yields and short-term rates in Nigeria contains signals about future inflation trends, although its

predictive power appears weaker than in advanced economies, partly because of liquidity constraints in Nigeria's bond market.

Lastly, research specifically focused on the term structure of bank deposit rates in Nigeria remains limited. However, the slope of this structure can reveal important insights into banks' expectations of funding costs and liquidity needs. In theory, a wider gap between 12-month and 1-month deposit rates suggests that banks are offering a premium for longer-term funds, possibly because they anticipate rising short-term rates or feel less pressure for immediate liquidity. However, a flat or inverted deposit rate slope, where short-term deposits yield as much as or more than one-year deposits, indicates strong demand for short-term liquidity, as banks bid up near-term rates relative to longer maturities. Such situations often arise during periods of monetary tightening or liquidity stress and can foreshadow short-term rate spikes if conditions persist. In summary, previous research shows that the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) is the main determinant of Nigerian money market rates, with Treasury bill and interbank rates most closely aligned to it. Although deviations from the policy benchmark are usually short-lived, their extent and duration can vary depending on market liquidity and expectations. Studies indicate that examining these deviations, such as the policy overhang (the gap between the MPR and T-bill yield), the interbank rate spread, or the deposit rate slope, can provide valuable predictive insights. Building on this foundation, this study tests the forecasting power of these spreads in explaining short-term movements in Treasury bill yields, offering a focused perspective on short-run interest rate dynamics in Nigeria.

3.0 Data and Methodology

This paper utilizes monthly time-series data spanning the period from 2006 to 2025. The dataset is sourced from official Central Bank of Nigeria statistics (Money Market Indicators), ensuring consistency and reliability. Key variables include: the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), the 91-day Treasury bill yield (primary market rate), the interbank call rate (weighted average overnight rate), and deposit rates for maturities of 1 month and 12 months (among other tenors). The sample comprises a total of 235 monthly observations. To analyse changes in Treasury bill (T-bill) yields, The paper defines the dependent variable as the month-on-month change in the 91-day T-bill rate, expressed in percentage points. Formally:

$$\Delta \text{Tbill}_t = \text{Tbill}_t - \text{Tbill}_{t-1}$$

As shown earlier in Figure 1 (see Introduction), T-bill yields generally move in tandem with the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), though some gaps persist over time. **Table 1** below summarizes key statistics for the variables included in the analysis, covering the period from 2006 to 2025.

Variable	Definition	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Key Insights
Policy Overhang	MPR–T-bill yield	3.93	5.38	–13.6	+16.1	On average, the policy rate (MPR) has stood about 4 percentage points above the 91-day T-bill yield. However, the wide standard deviation (5.4 pp) and the range (from –13.7 pp to +16.1 pp) show that large gaps, both negative and positive, occur frequently.
Interbank Liquidity Stress	Call rate – MPR	0.12	7.4	–15.5	+50.6	The average is essentially zero (0.12 pp), meaning the call rate usually hovers around the policy rate. But the extreme max of +50.6 pp highlights episodes of severe liquidity stress (e.g., crisis periods when overnight rates spiked massively). The large standard deviation (7.4 pp) indicates these stress episodes are rare but very impactful.
Funding Curve Slope/Deposit slope	12-month deposit – 1-month deposit	+0.62	1.88	–3.51	+7.01	The slope is usually positive (mean 0.62 pp), suggesting a “normal” term structure. But the fact that the slope turns negative (as low as –3.5 pp) shows that inversions do happen, signaling funding stress. The relatively low standard deviation (1.9 pp) means changes are modest most of the time, but inversions are meaningful when they appear.

Unit root tests show that $\Delta Tbill$ is stationary ($I(0)$), making it suitable as the dependent variable. Among the regressors, Policy Overhang appears non-stationary, while Interbank Stress and the Deposit Slope are best described as trend-stationary. This supports the use of $\Delta Tbill$ in predictive regressions and justifies interpreting the overhang as an error-correction term. Consequently, the paper proceeds with standard regression analysis without major concerns about spurious relationships arising from non-stationarity.

The baseline regression is specified as:

$$\Delta Tbill_t = \alpha + \beta_1 (MPR_{t-1} - Tbill_{t-1}) + \beta_2 (CallRate_{t-1} - MPR_{t-1}) + \beta_3 (Dep12_{t-1} - Dep1_{t-1}) + \varepsilon$$

Where $\Delta Tbill_t$ represents the monthly change in the Treasury bill yield, the explanatory variables capture monetary policy and market conditions from the previous month ($t-1$):

- $(MPR_{t-1} - Tbill_{t-1})$: the policy overhang, reflecting the gap between the policy rate and the short-term market rate.
- $(CallRate_{t-1} - MPR_{t-1})$: interbank liquidity stress, representing overnight market conditions relative to policy rates.
- $(Dep12_{t-1} - Dep1_{t-1})$: the funding curve slope/deposit slope, indicating the relative pricing of short- and long-term deposits.

The predictors are lagged one month so that information from period $t-1$ is used to forecast T-bill changes in t , reducing simultaneity bias. A constant term (α) captures any average drift, and Newey–West HAC errors with a 12-month lag window are applied to correct for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation common in monthly interest rate data. All estimations were performed using standard statistical packages, with results emphasizing economic significance and policy relevance.

4.0 Empirical Results

Table 2 reports the estimation results from the baseline regression, obtained using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) with Newey–West HAC standard errors.

Variable	Coefficient (Sign)	Significance	Interpretation / Economic Meaning
Policy Overhang (MPR – T-bill)	+0.13	$p \approx 0.02$ (5% level)	Statistically significant and positive. About 13% of the gap between the policy rate and T-bill yield closes each month, confirming the error-correction mechanism where market yields adjust upward when below the policy rate.
Interbank Liquidity Stress (Call – MPR)	+0.04	$p \approx 0.05-0.06$ (~10% level)	Positive but marginally significant. Indicates that tighter liquidity (call rate above MPR) leads to higher T-bill yields in the next month. Effects are short-lived, often offset by central bank intervention.
Funding Curve Slope (12m – 1m Deposit)	-0.15	$p \approx 0.05$ (5% level)	Negative and significant. Significant and negative. A steeper deposit curve (12m > 1m) signals comfortable liquidity and predicts lower short-term yields, while inversions anticipate upward pressure.
Constant Term	-0.53	$p \approx 0.04$ (5% level)	Suggests a small average downward drift in yields not explained by spreads.

Model Fit (R²) 0.08 — About 8% of the variation in monthly T-bill yield changes is explained by the model, modest but typical for financial time-series. Predictors remain economically meaningful and correctly signed.

Joint F-Test (Model — $p \approx 0.058$ Indicates marginal joint significance of predictors. Model captures consistent, directional effects amid market noise.
Significance)

4.1 Extended Empirical Results

4.1.1 Policy Overhang Channel (Simple HAC-OLS Model)

To test whether the policy overhang alone predicts yield changes, The paper estimates a HAC-robust OLS regression of next-month T-bill yield changes on the lagged MPR-T-bill spread:

$$\Delta TBill_t = \alpha + \beta (MPR_{t-1} - TBill_{t-1}) + \varepsilon_t$$

Statistic	Result
Coefficient (β)	+0.084
t-statistic	2.42
p-value	0.015
R ²	0.048
N	234

The coefficient is positive and statistically significant, indicating that when the MPR exceeds the 91-day T-bill yield, the latter tends to rise in the following month. Economically, a 1 percentage-point policy overhang predicts an 8.4 basis-point increase in T-bill yields on average. While the model explains about 5% of monthly yield variation. To validate the behavioral logic of the policy overhang model, The paper applied a **directional accuracy test**. This approach compares the sign of the lagged MPR-T-bill spread with the direction of subsequent changes in T-bill yields:

- When overhang > 0, T-bill yields rose **41%** of the time.
- When overhang < 0, yields fell **64%** of the time.

This asymmetry shows that markets correct more quickly when yields exceed the policy rate than when policy tightening leads market adjustment.

4.1.2 Expanded Models: Liquidity and Funding Channels

To isolate other short-term drivers, The paper estimate single- and two-predictor HAC–OLS models using lagged spreads. The key findings are:

Variable	Sign	Interpretation
Policy overhang (MPR – T-bill)	Positive, significant ($\beta \approx 0.08$, $p < 0.02$)	Confirms error-correction behavior between policy and market rates.
Interbank tightness (Call – MPR)	Positive, variable significance	Higher funding costs push up T-bill yields, especially in tight markets.
Deposit slope (12m – 1m deposits)	Negative	Steeper curves (liquidity comfort) predict easing in short-term yields.

When tightness and the deposit slope are included together (excluding overhang), both retain their expected signs, confirming that liquidity and funding conditions independently shape short-term yield movements alongside policy stance.

4.1.3 Stress-State Heterogeneity

The paper further assesses how these relationships differ between “normal” and “stress” periods, where stress months are defined by the call rate exceeding the 75th percentile of its spread over the MPR. Results show that the policy overhang effect remains positive and stable across both regimes, with slightly faster adjustment under stress that converges by six months. In contrast, interbank tightness raises T-bill yields in normal times but weakens or reverses under stress, consistent with corrective liquidity injections. The interaction model confirms this reversal (interaction term $p \approx 0.03$). The deposit slope remains negative in both states, with stronger effects under stress (interaction $p \approx 0.09$), suggesting that steeper curves more strongly signal near-term easing when markets are strained.

Finally, the paper employ **Jordà-style local projections** to examine how the effects of each variable evolve over 1–to 6-month horizons (Jordà, 2005).

The patterns are intuitive and consistent.

Predictor	Dynamic Response/	Interpretation
Policy Overhang	Monotonic positive path	Large positive gaps close gradually over several months, confirming the error-correction mechanism.

Interbank Tightness	Short-lived but accumulative	Yield increases persist if stress remains, though uncertainty widens over time.
Deposit Slope	Persistently negative	Steeper curves today forecast softer yields ahead; inversions signal tightening pressure.

The combination of OLS estimation, HAC-robust standard errors, and Jordà-style local projections shows that, although monthly yield movements are often noisy, the underlying relationship between policy rates and market yields remains stable and economically meaningful. Multiple diagnostic and robustness checks confirm the consistency of these results across different model specifications and time horizon.

4.1.4 Robustness Checks

Alternative error specifications using different HAC bandwidths (6- and 12-month) and clustering by quarter confirm the stability of the estimates. The policy overhang and deposit slope remain significant across all settings, while interbank tightness is marginally significant, particularly under clustered errors, suggesting the inference is not sensitive to covariance assumptions. Splitting the sample into 2006–2015 and 2016–2025 shows that the policy overhang effect strengthened in the latter period (β rising from ≈ 0.06 to ≈ 0.24), consistent with tighter policy signaling during high-inflation years. The call–MPR spread becomes more informative after 2015, while the deposit slope turns negative and gains significance, reflecting deeper liquidity and funding interactions. Finally, removing the top 1% of call spread observations or the single highest month leaves results unchanged. The persistence of coefficient signs and magnitudes confirms that no single outlier or episode drives the findings, supporting the robustness of the model’s predictive structure. In summary, the robustness checks reinforce the confidence in the baseline findings. The policy overhang effect is very robust, consistently indicating that T-bill yields adjust toward the MPR. The liquidity and funding indicators also retain their predictive content under various conditions, though their statistical significance is somewhat sensitive to sample period and the presence of extreme liquidity events.

5.0 Discussion of Findings

The empirical results reveal the multi-channel nature of short-term interest rate dynamics in Nigeria’s money market. Each of the three spread indicators; policy overhang, interbank liquidity stress, and the deposit slope plays a distinct but complementary role in shaping Treasury bill (T-bill) yield movements. Together, these factors illustrate how monetary policy signals, liquidity pressures, and banks’ funding preferences interact to influence the pricing of short-term government securities. The policy overhang, defined as the spread between the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) and the T-bill yield, emerges as the most robust determinant of yield changes. The estimated coefficients indicate that approximately 8–15 percent of the gap between the policy rate and market yields is corrected each month, implying a gradual error-correction process. This confirms that market rates tend to converge toward the policy stance over time. The adjustment, however, is asymmetric: when market yields exceed the MPR, the correction occurs more quickly than when policy rates are above market rates. This pattern suggests that liquidity surpluses and credibility lags slow the pass-through of policy tightening, while market corrections to excess yields are more immediate. Persistent positive overhangs therefore signal incomplete transmission, while for investors, the magnitude of the spread provides a useful gauge of near-term yield direction.

Interbank liquidity stress, measured by the call–MPR spread, also exerts an important influence, though its effect is more episodic. Positive spreads, where interbank rates exceed the policy rate, are associated with subsequent increases in T-bill yields, reflecting the transmission of liquidity shortages into broader money market conditions. The deposit rate slope (12-month minus 1-month) provides a complementary signal reflecting the structure of bank funding conditions. The negative and statistically significant coefficient indicates that a steeper deposit curve (where long-term deposits yield more than short-term ones) tends to precede lower near-term T-bill yields. However, a flat or inverted slope, where short-term deposits command higher rates, predicts upward pressure on T-bill yields. This finding suggests that when banks are willing to pay more for short-term funds, liquidity conditions are tight, and stress soon transmits to the government securities market. Local projection estimates further reveal that this funding-slope effect persists over several months, implying that it serves as a medium-term indicator of liquidity tension rather than an immediate one.

Overall, these findings emphasize that short-term interest rate behavior in Nigeria is driven by the interaction of policy stance, liquidity conditions, and funding structures. The policy rate provides the central anchor through the error-correction mechanism, while interbank and deposit spreads shape the timing and strength of market adjustment. For policymakers, this stresses the importance of coordinated liquidity management to ensure effective policy transmission. For investors, the identified spreads offer practical guidance: large positive policy overhangs tend to push yields upward, negative overhangs correct quickly, sustained call–MPR spreads indicate tightening pressures, and inverted deposit slopes signal persistent stress. Collectively, the results confirm that short-term spreads in Nigeria’s money market carry significant predictive information, offering insights into both policy effectiveness and market expectations.

5.1 Conclusion

This paper has investigated the drivers of short-term Treasury bill yield changes in Nigeria between 2006 and 2025, focusing on three spread indicators: policy overhang (MPR – T-bill), interbank liquidity stress (Call – MPR), and the funding curve slope (12m – 1m deposits). The results show that the policy overhang is the most robust and statistically significant predictor, with roughly 8–15 percent of the gap between the policy rate and market yields closing each month. This confirms an error-correction process that anchors T-bill yields to monetary policy, though the adjustment is asymmetric—yields correct faster when above the policy rate than when below it. Liquidity stress in the interbank market plays a meaningful role, exerting disproportionate influence during episodes of market strain. Meanwhile, the deposit slope consistently signals bank funding pressures that affect sovereign yields. Together, these findings underline that Nigeria’s short-term interest rates are shaped not only by the Central Bank’s policy stance but also by liquidity dynamics and funding preferences within the banking system. For policymakers, the implication is that ensuring effective transmission requires more than setting the MPR: it demands close monitoring of interbank spreads and funding curves to detect stress early and guide interventions. For investors, the spreads provide practical, forward-looking indicators of yield direction, offering opportunities to anticipate corrections and manage portfolio risk. In this way, spread analysis enhances both policy effectiveness and investment strategy, showing that even in a shallow and volatile money market, predictable relationships can be harnessed to improve outcomes.

References

- Awopegba, O., Afolabi, J., Adeoye, L., & Akpokodje, G. (2022). Effect of Monetary Policy Rate on Market Interest Rates in Nigeria: A Threshold and NARDL Approach. *Central Bank of Nigeria Journal of Applied Statistics*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.33429/cjas.13122.4/9>
- Bernanke, B. S., & Mihov, I. (1998). Measuring Monetary Policy. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 113(3), 869–902. JSTOR. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2586876>
- Cottarelli, C., & Kourelis, A. (1994). Financial Structure, Bank Lending Rates, and the Transmission Mechanism of Monetary Policy. *Staff Papers - International Monetary Fund*, 41(4), 587. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3867521>
- Engle, R. F., & Granger, C. W. J. (1987). Co-Integration and Error Correction: Representation, Estimation, and Testing. *Econometrica*, 55(2), 251–276.
- Hardouvelis, G. A. (1994). The term structure spread and future changes in long and short rates in the G7 countries. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 33(2), 255–283. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(94\)90003-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(94)90003-5)
- Hendry, D. F., Pagan, A., & Sargan, J. D. (1984). *Chapter 18 Dynamic specification*. 1023–1100. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1573-4412\(84\)02010-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1573-4412(84)02010-9)
- Jordà, Ò. (2005). Estimation and Inference of Impulse Responses by Local Projections. *American Economic Review*, 95(1), 161–182. <https://doi.org/10.1257/0002828053828518>
- Kelilume, I. (2014). Effects of the monetary policy rate on interest rates in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Business and Finance Research*, 8(1), 45-55.
- Mishkin, Frederic S. 1990. “What Does the Term Structure Tell Us About Future Inflation?” *Journal of Monetary Economics* 25 (January): 77-95.
- Saidu, S. A., Aliyu, B. S., & Zubair, A. U. (2018). Does changes in monetary policy rate in Nigeria have effect on interest rates? recent evidence. *CBN Bullion*, 42(3), 69-88.
- Samuel Oluwapelumi, O., Olusegun Samuel, A., & Cecilia Oluwakemi Aina, O. (2021). The Impact of Monetary Policy on Assets Management of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 9(3), 60. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jfa.20210903.11>
- Sanusi, A. R. (2010, November). Interest rate pass-through and the efficiency of monetary policy in Nigeria: 2002-2010. In National Conference on State of the Nigerian Economy.

